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Gender “CAN”[(^C)reative (^A)daptabe (^N)etwork]

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Abstract

The present study has tried to explore the relationship between three important professional skills i.e. networking skills, adaptable skills and creativity with gender. It tries to study whether these skills do have some impact on sustaining the job. The present employable generation inhibit, learn & practice employable skill to get job & to sustain in the job and in this process, do really gender play an crucial impact on learning / practising these skills at study place / work place. Hence this study tries to find out the effect between gender and CAN skills like networking, adaptability and creativity along with a very basic question to explore; whether a professor should recommend a student to prospective employer both from the students & corporate group.

Key words: *Employment Issues in India, Networking skill, Adaptable Skill, Creativity*

INTRODUCTION

The growth of Indian economy has positively dependent on the employment condition in the country. [9] Unemployment may be defined as the number of people looking for a fresh job or a new job with a record of 3.8 percent in December of 2011. [15] According to World Fact book, the unemployment rate of India is 9.9% which need to be address by providing solutions for the students with the required skill that enable them to be employed. [16] Verbal/Written communication, Teamwork, Ability to analyse & interpret, self motivation, flexibility, time management are the top ranked skills mentioned by university of Kent, after a rigorous research work. [14] Networking is Everything, by enabling the youth to increase contacts & chances of getting employment.[12] Network is a system to interconnected with people & getting benefits from the group members, can do for you while networking is a continuous process of making,

sustaining connections and an important components of any profession. [10] Networking skills include communication, negotiation, influencing & motivational, leadership & assertiveness, enabling a job seeker to reach to its destination rapidly.[3] Networking is not a game of WHAT you know rather it became a game of WHO you know or WHO knows you well. Maximum job vacancies are not advertised & employers fill them with people who approached them directly with a reference hence there is a huge need of networking skill required by the job seeker. Networking helps in establishing a clear understanding of the job role through mentoring, suggesting improvements, provide all relevant information regarding job, recommending the sources of information & researching companies.[5]According to Charles Darwin *“It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most intelligent that survives. It is the one that is the most adaptable to change”*. Adaptability is the basic differences between adapting to cope & adapting to win. [1]Today's organizations are characterized by changing, dynamic environments in which the need for adaptive workers has become increasingly important (Edwards & Morrison, 1994; Ilgen & Pulakos, 1999; Smith, Ford, & Kozlowski, 1997). In a global economy, many jobs require individuals to learn to operate effectively in a variety of different countries and with individual who possess different values and orientations than themselves (Black, 1990; Noe & Ford, 1992). Many authors have discussed adaptability (see, e.g., Ilgen & Pulakos, 1999) in relation to different phenomena at the individual, team, and organizational levels, often using many different names and definitions for this concept. For example, Hesketh and Neal (1999) referred to adaptive performance, P. R. Murphy and Jackson (1999) discussed role flexibility, and London and Mone (1999) wrote about the proficiency with which individuals self manage their new learning experiences. Furthermore, adaptation has been discussed in relation to many different organizationally relevant variables (e.g., new people and teams, novel and ill defined problems, different cultures, new technology, challenging Physical conditions), encompassing a wide range of behaviours across a variety of different task demands. [8] Oxford dictionary define creativity with original ideas to create something or the use of imagination to invent a new things/product/services. Creativity may also be defined as a sequence of action which generates new ideas, thoughts & physical objects. [6] In 21st century organisational setup, the leaders/managers/executive is expected to be able to reflect creatively and provide unique resolution at work place. Creative employee can foster better teamwork and can establish team building, develop workplace engagement and interaction, ability to catch the

attention & retain employees and may increase productivity. [11] Creativity & innovation are basically required for organisational success in a dynamic global economy. Creativity has not always been seen as playing & designing the structure of the organisation but it is a key requirement for the growth & adaption of the 21st century organisation. (Dr. Michael d. Mumford and Dr. Dean Keith Simonton, 1997). [13] Positive Attitude, Ability to communicate, flexibility, self motivation, innovative ideas, R & D activities Knowledge of Market Research, Networking & Industrial training are considered as the important in today's corporate world (Choudhury, M & Sharma, P, 2014) [4] Creative dimensions like providing time & rewards for creativity, motivating risk taking, multiplicity of thinking, cooperation and questioning of assumptions can also be successfully integrated into the business education. (Michaela Driver, 2001). [7] It can be enhanced by great many techniques like the cutting of people's ties, using computers for electronic brainstorming, thinking hats, painting of room with vivid colour to stimulate creative thinking (TM Amabile, 1996). [2]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Jacquelyn P. Robinson, Community Workforce, Development Specialist, State Headquarters, 216 Extension Hall, Auburn University, AL, 36849-5631, in his work "The Workplace – A Fact sheet What are employability skills" clustered job skill into 3 skill sets as Basic Academic Skills, Higher order Thinking Skills & Personal Qualities and highlighted on Skill- Gap.

Lai Wan Hooi, Centre for Technology Policy and International Studies, University Teknologi Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, in his study "The adoption of Japanese recruitment practices in Malaysia" find the existence of some consistent sets of recruitment behaviour among the companies, though it cannot be said with much confidence that these patterns are indeed representative of Malaysian recruitment behaviour.

Mohamed Branine, Dundee Business School, University of Abertay Dundee, Dundee, UK in his study Graduate recruitment and selection in the UK : A study of the recent changes in methods and expectations, find that all employers, regardless of organisation size or activity type, tend to use more sophisticated, objective and cost-effective methods of recruitment and selection than before. The process of graduate recruitment and selection in the UK has become more person-related than job-oriented because many employers are more interested in the attitudes,

personality and transferable skills of applicants than the type or level of qualification acquired. Although some of the usual methods such as interviewing remain popular, there is a greater variety of ways by which graduates are attracted to and selected for their first jobs.

Arnaldo Camuffo- Department of Management, Bocconi University, Milan, Italy, Fabrizio Gerli - Department of Business Economics and Management, Ca’ Foscari University of Venice, Venice, Italy, and Silvia Borgo and Tatiana Somia- CUOA Foundation, Altavilla Vicentina, Italy in their study The effects of management education on careers and compensation -A competency-based study of an Italian MBA Programme. Their findings support the hypothesis that the degree of competency development during the MBA programme enhances career advancement, and that some competencies, like planning, result orientation, networking, organizational awareness, system thinking and use of technology, do so particularly, which is consistent with literature on career competencies. No relationship is found, instead, between competency development during the MBA and compensation.

Tracy Harkison, Jill Poulston and Jung-Hee Ginny Kim ,Faculty of Applied Humanities, School of Hospitality and Tourism, AUT University, Auckland, New Zealand Hospitality graduates and managers: the big divide, resulted the views between students and industry was significant. Students thought knowledge and skills were important for new employees, but industry was far more interested in personality. To get promoted, students thought they would have to become good communicators, but industry was more interested in initiative. Industry’s views suggest that managers value attitudinal attributes over skills, and are therefore prepared to help employees gain the skills needed for their roles.

Stuart Rosenberg- Department of Management and Marketing, Leon Hess Business School, Monmouth University, West Long Branch, New Jersey, USA, Ronald Heimler - College of Agriculture, California State Polytechnic University, Pomona, California, USA, and Elsa-Sofia Morote - Department of Educational Administration, Leadership, and Technology, Dowling College, Oakdale, New York, USA in their study Basic employability skills: a triangular design approach. The study revealed considerable differences in opinion among the three groups with regard to the skills needed for job performance, the skills received by college graduates, and the additional training needed. Although the respondents identified the importance of leadership skills, these skills were noted to be below expectations for industry.

Moreover, the need for additional training of recent graduates appears to be a major concern according to the results.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This paper tries to find out the relationship, if exist between gender and CAN skills (such as like networking, adaptability and creativity) & with a very basic question to explore; whether a professor should recommend a student to prospective employer or not, both from the students & corporate group.

HYPOTHESIS

H1 There is a relationship between networking skill, Adaptability Skill and Creativity with Gender.

H2 There is a relationship with Adaptability skill and experience.

METHODOLGY

Keeping the objective in mind the author has collected responses online only through Google doc(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1NXTL4T6AKpHIBIEYS17hoLuY2_0UD0oBjtCOH6n-JzU/viewform) from renowned Academicians of AICTE & UGC affiliated management colleges and also approached the corporate profile who is involved into the hiring process to contribute their views online by adopting **Non probability sampling technique** by utilising the authors own social media such as Linked In, Google groups, Face book groups & e-mail directly to the other list of participants. The sample size were determined 5 per variable (Kass & Tinsley,1979). All the variables were measured & validated through “Content Validity” methodology. The Research approach is pragmatic in nature. The Google form has sent to more than 1000 adequate profile to collect responses & only 160 responses have collected after filtering the unutilised responses. The data collection has been done after pre-test with 10 Academicians & 5 Corporate members to access the content adequacy, including appropriateness of the questions, scales & instructions given. Based on the Pre-test feedback the questionnaire was slightly modified to achieve the research objectives. A Pilot test has been conducted with 20 responses which include

Academician, Student & Corporate to examine statistical and methodological accuracy which also includes the reliability & Validity of the scale.

All the constructs were measured on seven point Likert scale, anchored from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (7). Respondents were asked to fill the responses the degree to which they believe that they would recruit or recommend or possess management graduate with skills.

DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

Before the actual data analysis, the final data has been prepared by recoding the missing values by the means of same variable of different items measured for these test. The variables were standardised using Z score.

Table 1 explaining the demographic profile of the respondent in this study. Out of 151 respondents 63.6% are male (N=96) & 36.4% are female (N=55). 25.2% are people have experience from 1-5 years (n=38), 15.9% people have 6-10 years (n=24), 7.3% of respondent having the experience group of 10-15 years (n=11), 4.6% of responses (n=7) having experience of 16-20 years, 12.6% responses (n=19) having experience more than 21 years of experience where as 34.4% (n=52) are not working. 42.4% of the respondent (n=64) belongs to age group of 20-25, 18.5% of the respondent (n=28) belongs to age group of 26-30, 14.6% of the respondent (n=22) belongs to age group of 31-35, 6.6% of the respondent (n=10) belongs to age group of 36-40, 7.9% of the respondent (n=12) belongs to age group of 41-45 and only 9.9% of the respondent (n=15) belongs to age group of 46 years & above.

To find out our objective, whether the professor should recommend students to the corporate or not both from the students concern & corporate concern, we calculate the mean score which find not to be difference. In **table 2**, we can see that the corporate mean score is 5.53 & the Student Mean score is 5.61, the effect size is -0.027699313349414483, which is calculated through Cohen's d test. But if we look into the frequency distribution in **table 3** we can find that 50% of the corporate agrees to get the recommendation from the institute professors, where as 30.6% of the students would like to get recommendation from their professors during a placement.

To prove the Hypothesis that, there is a relationship between networking skill, Adaptability Skill and Creativity with Gender (H1) the Point-Biserial correlation coefficient (Bivariate Correlation) test performed and it is found that the test is not significant and there is no significant

relationship between Adaptability skills, Networking skills, and Creativity with Gender. The test is not significant and there is no significant relationship between gender & creativity, $r_{(pb)} = .007$, $p(1\text{-tailed}) > .05$. The test is not significant and there is negative significant relationship between gender & Adaptability, $r_{(pb)} = -.095$, $p(1\text{-tailed}) > .05$. The test is not significant and there is no significant relationship between gender & Networking skill, $r_{(pb)} = .032$, $p(1\text{-tailed}) > .05$. (Table – 4), hence the H1 is rejected. To prove the H2 spearman's rho performed and the test is not significant and there is no significant relationship between Experience & Adaptability skill, $\rho = .026$, $p(2\text{-tailed}) > .05$. (Table-5) hence the H1 is rejected. To prove the hypothesis that, there is a relationship with Adaptability skill and experience i performed ANOVA (Donaldson, 1968) and $F(5, 150) = .379$, $p > .05$ and found that the test is not significant and there is no significant relationship with experience & adaptability skill. Hence the H2 is rejected (Table-6).

6. CONCLUSION

The corporate agree the recommendations from the professors before hiring students. The Gender has no relationship with creativity. Gender has negative relationship with Networking skill and Adaptability skill. The Experience has no relationship between the adaptability skills. Hence the students may develop these Skills which are highly preferably employable skills [3, 4, 6, 10, 12, and 13]

7. DISCUSSION & LIMITATIONS

The research findings also lack max responses, however if the number of responses could be increased more the research findings & its effect would have been implemented globally.

8. APPENDIX

Table -1

Sample Characteristics	Frequency (N=151)	Percent %
Gender		
Male	96	63.6
Female	55	36.4
Group Belongs to		
Academic	55	36.4
Corporate	34	22.5
Student	62	41.1
Experience in Years		
1-5 Years	38	25.2
6-10 Years	24	15.9
10-15 Years	11	7.3
16-20 Years	7	4.6
21 Years & above	19	12.6
NIL	52	34.4
Age		
20-25	64	42.4
26-30	28	18.5
31-35	22	14.6
36-40	10	6.6
41-45	12	7.9
46 & above	15	9.9

Table -2

Group	Corporate	Student
Mean	5.53	5.61
Standard error of mean	.246	.184
Standard deviation	1.435	1.452
Cohen's d	-0.05541989128854404	
Effect size	-0.027699313349414483	

Table -3

Group Belongs		Frequency	Percent
Corporate	Valid	1	2.9
		2	5.9
		3	5.9
		4	11.8
		5	5.9
		6	50.0
		7	17.6
		Total	34
Student	Valid	1	1.6
		2	6.5
		3	6.5
		4	22.6
		5	1.6
		6	30.6
		7	30.6
		Total	62

Table-4

		Correlations				
			Gender	Creativity	Adaptability	Networking skills
Spearman's rho	Gender	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.007	-.095	-.032
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	.468	.123	.348
		N	151	151	151	151

Table- 5

		Correlations		
			Adaptability	Exp
Spearman's rho	Adaptability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.026
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.753
		N	151	151
	Exp	Correlation Coefficient	.026	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.753	.
		N	151	151

Table-6

ANOVA					
Adaptability					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.189	5	.438	.379	.863
Within Groups	167.526	145	1.155		
Total	169.715	150			

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